

REDEFINING LANGUAGE LEARNING: INTEGRATING PERFORMANCE-BASED PEDAGOGY TO FOSTER DYNAMIC 21ST CENTURY SPEAKING SKILLS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 2

Pages: 115-129

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2246

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13362014

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

Redefining Language Learning: Integrating Performance-Based Pedagogy to Foster Dynamic 21st Century Speaking Skills

Girlie S. Gorgonia,* Kristine May De Vera Casibang
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research focused on investigating the effect of integrating Performance-Based Pedagogy, an approach to teaching and learning that emphasizes students being able to do or perform specific skills because of instruction, in enhancing the 21st-century public speaking skills of Senior High School learners, specifically in terms of delivering prepared and extemporaneous speeches. This study employed a true-experimental research design to further explore the effectiveness of narrative pedagogy in reducing the affective filter and enhancing speaking skills among learners. The research findings indicated that the Experimental Group with students exposed to the performance-based speaking activities tended to have a higher proportion of students scoring Excellent in both types of speeches, while the Controlled Group had more students scoring in the Good range. These findings underscored the effectiveness of Performance-Based intervention, as evidenced by the superior performance of the Experimental Group, thereby emphasizing the importance of innovative pedagogical approaches in enhancing students' public speaking skills. The findings revealed the superior performance of the Experimental Group in both prepared and extemporaneous speeches, highlighting the effectiveness of Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing the 21st-century skills of Senior High School students. The study highly recommends the integration of performance-based activities into the curriculum and the exploration of alternative approaches for enhancing extemporaneous speech skills. The proposed action plan emphasizes experiential learning and feedback mechanisms to foster articulate and confident 21st-century communicators.

Keywords: *performance-based pedagogy, speaking skills, 21st century speaking skills*

Introduction

In the contemporary landscape of the 21st century, there exists a recognized set of skills crucial for thriving in today's workforce. Termed "21st century skills," these encompass a blend of competencies and knowledge considered essential for success in professional endeavors. The American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL, 2021) has been instrumental in defining and advocating for these skills. Through their creation of a comprehensive map, they provide educators, administrators, and policymakers with a practical framework for integrating these skills into language education.

Among the array of 21st century skills, certain core competencies emerge: critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, digital literacy, information literacy, adaptability, problem-solving, and notably, communication. The emphasis on communication, particularly speaking proficiency, is notable as it acknowledges the interconnected nature of our global society.

According to the study conducted by Leonita et al. (2023) titled "Speaking Skill in 21st-Century: Students' Perceptions And Challenges In English Language Teaching", 21st century speaking skills encompass a set of communication abilities essential for effectively engaging in diverse personal, professional, and academic contexts in the contemporary era. These skills go beyond traditional oratory proficiency, incorporating a range of components tailored to the demands of modern communication channels and environments. They include but are not limited to clarity, coherence, and conciseness in verbal expression, and fluency or the ability of speakers to convey their ideas comprehensively and persuasively. Additionally, adaptability and versatility are key characteristics, allowing speakers to adjust their communication style and content to suit different audiences, purposes, and platforms, whether in face-to-face interactions, virtual settings, or multimedia presentations. In the same study, they added that proficiency in nonverbal communication, such as body language, gestures, and facial expressions, enhances message delivery and reception, as well as audience connection, enriching the overall communicative experience.

In the evolving landscape of the 21st century, the demand for proficient speaking skills transcends national borders, driven by factors both international and local (Bax, 2017). Globally, the rapid expansion of technology and communication networks has facilitated unprecedented levels of interconnectedness, transforming the dynamics of business, education, and societal interaction (OECD, 2018).

Internationally, the globalization of industries has spurred a heightened need for effective cross-cultural communication (Choudhury, 2018). As businesses expand their operations across continents and cultures, the ability to articulate ideas clearly and persuasively becomes paramount. Multinational corporations seek employees who can navigate linguistic and cultural nuances with ease, fostering collaboration and synergy across diverse teams (McNeil, 2018).

Moreover, the proliferation of digital platforms has democratized communication on a global scale (UNESCO, 2015). Social media, online forums, and virtual collaboration tools have become integral to everyday interactions, necessitating proficiency in spoken communication to effectively convey messages and build relationships in virtual spaces.

On a local level, the importance of 21st century speaking skills is underscored by demographic shifts and multiculturalism within communities (UNESCO, 2015). In increasingly diverse societies, individuals encounter a mosaic of languages and cultural backgrounds in their daily interactions. Effective communication, particularly oral proficiency, serves as a bridge that fosters understanding and cohesion amidst this diversity.

Within educational contexts, both globally and locally, there is a growing recognition of the need to equip learners with strong speaking skills to thrive in the 21st century (ACTFL, 2021). Language education curricula are evolving to emphasize interactive and communicative approaches that prioritize oral proficiency alongside other essential skills. In the realm of employment, the ability to communicate articulately and persuasively has emerged as a non-negotiable competency across industries (OECD, 2018). Employers seek candidates who can effectively convey ideas, collaborate with colleagues, and engage with clients and stakeholders, recognizing the pivotal role of speaking skills in driving organizational success.

In summary, the international and local context of 21st century speaking skills is shaped by the imperatives of globalization, technological advancement, cultural diversity, and evolving educational and professional landscapes. Mastery of speaking skills is not only a means of navigating these complexities but also a catalyst for personal and professional growth in an interconnected world.

Despite the recognized importance of 21st century speaking skills, ESL learners continue to face challenges in acquiring them, as revealed in studies such as "ESL Learners' Challenges in Speaking English in Malaysian Classroom" (Kashinathan & Aziz, 2021). Internal and external hurdles hinder ESL students' English speaking development, with previous studies highlighting limitations and proposing future research directions.

In Malaysia, the lack of 21st century communication skills among ESL students is a pressing issue (Spawa & Hassan, 2018). Traditional teaching methods often hinder students' proficiency in the target language, leading to poor speaking performance. Similarly, in Saudi Arabia, the role of teachers is crucial in developing speaking fluency, advocating for student-centered approaches (Mohamed, 2022).

English as a second language presents significant challenges, requiring collaborative efforts from learners and educators (Khashbani, 2018). The shift towards a communicative approach in Malaysian higher education aims to enhance speaking and listening skills, recognizing the importance of communication in everyday life (Zakaria & Shah, 2019).

The COVID-19 pandemic has further impacted ESL learners' speaking skills, disrupting traditional learning environments (Verwadina et al., 2020). Factors such as anxiety, teaching techniques, and cultural influences contribute to ESL students' reluctance to use the target language (Savasci, 2013; Idrus & Salleh, 2007).

In the Philippines, declining English-speaking proficiency among Senior High School learners necessitates intervention (Tindowen et al., 2017). Observations indicate a decline in speaking skills, attributed to linguistic, cognitive, and socio-emotional factors (Silva, 2019). Limited exposure to English outside the classroom and the influence of local languages contribute to difficulties in articulating thoughts and ideas in English, highlighting the need to address these challenges promptly.

The decline in English-speaking proficiency among Senior High School (SHS) learners is evident, attributed to various challenges within the education system and societal influences (Tambunan et al., 2017). Anxiety and self-insecurity hinder speaking skill development, stemming from fear of judgment and linguistic insecurities.

According to Cabigon (2015), learners perceive speaking as challenging due to vocabulary and grammatical deficiencies, leading to hesitation in verbal expression and diminished confidence. Curriculum designers and policymakers are urged to prioritize fluency over accuracy, emphasizing interpersonal and presentation skills to enhance students' speaking abilities (Krishnan et al., 2012).

Traditional teaching methods that prioritize memorization impede students' acquisition of 21st century speaking skills (Akbari, 2016). Experiential learning environments and tailored learning strategies are advocated to enhance communication skills and provide better learning experiences (Krishnan et al., 2012).

Hence, this study aimed to test the effect of a teaching approach to allow students to actively engage in real-world scenarios, fostering critical thinking, communication, and collaboration making them more capable of improving their 21st century English speaking skills. In this study, a teaching approach called Performance-Based Pedagogy was utilized and tested for its effectivity in the 21st century speaking skills of Senior High School learners.

Kelly (2019) defined Performance-Based pedagogy as an approach when students participate in performing tasks or activities that are meaningful and engaging. The aim of this type of learning is to enable students to gain and apply knowledge, practice skills, and build both independent and collaborative work habits. The final activity or project in performance-based learning allows students to show evidence of their understanding by applying their skills in a practical context.

Moreover, a TESOL (2022) article titled "How to Use Performance-Based Activities with Young Learners" added that Performance-Based pedagogy has a similar methodology and roots in task-based learning, in that the focus is on encouraging students to practice applying their language skills to multiple situations. Additionally, Hibbard (2020) in his article "Teacher's Guide to Performance-Based Learning and Assessment," noted that performance-based pedagogy focuses on teaching methods that ensure students can perform specific skills as a result of instruction. In this approach, students show their ability to apply or utilize knowledge rather than

just memorizing it. Performance-based learning often involves activities and tasks that are genuine and relevant to the students. The advantage of these assessments is that students who engage more actively in the learning process tend to absorb and comprehend the material more thoroughly. Other characteristics of performance-based assessments are that they are complex and time-bound (Gaudry-Routledge & Binder, 2018).

In the realm of language acquisition, particularly in the enhancement of students' speaking skills, Kayi (2016) emphasizes the pivotal role of Performance-Based Pedagogy. Speaking proficiency is not merely an academic requirement; it is a crucial life skill with far-reaching implications. Kayi underscores that proficiency in a second language enables individuals to navigate various spheres of life effectively, from academic endeavors to professional pursuits. Hence, language educators bear the responsibility of prioritizing speaking instruction. Rather than fostering rote memorization, educators should cultivate environments conducive to meaningful communication. Through a diverse array of speaking activities and performance-based tasks, students can develop fundamental interactive skills indispensable for real-life scenarios. These activities not only foster active participation but also imbue learning with significance and enjoyment for students.

By shifting the focus from passive learning to active engagement, performance-based approaches engender a dynamic classroom atmosphere where students are encouraged to express themselves authentically. Kayi (2016) advocates for the creation of environments where communication is not just a means to an end but an integral part of the learning process itself. Through this paradigm shift, students not only enhance their linguistic abilities but also acquire invaluable social and cognitive skills. Moreover, by integrating speaking activities into the curriculum, educators facilitate a holistic learning experience that resonates beyond the confines of the classroom. In essence, Performance-Based Pedagogy serves as a catalyst for empowering students to become proficient communicators equipped for the challenges of academic pursuits and the complexities of everyday life.

Further, Gallagher (2014) stated that Performance-Based pedagogy offers a dynamic approach to enhancing students' 21st century speaking skills by immersing them in active learning experiences. Through activities such as debates, presentations, role-plays, and simulations, students not only practice speaking but also develop critical thinking, collaboration, and communication skills essential for success in the modern world. By engaging in various speaking scenarios, students learn to articulate their ideas effectively, adapt their communication style to different audiences, and think on their feet.

Moreover, Performance-Based Pedagogy fosters creativity and confidence, encouraging students to express themselves authentically and explore diverse perspectives. As students receive constructive feedback and reflect on their performances, they refine their speaking abilities and become more adept at conveying their thoughts persuasively and compellingly. Ultimately, performance-based pedagogy cultivates a generation of articulate, adaptable, and empowered communicators equipped to thrive in the complex, interconnected landscape of the 21st century.

While previous studies have explored the effectiveness of Performance-Based Pedagogy, the specific focus on its impact on the 21st century speaking skills of SHS Filipino learners remains a research gap. Hence, this study entitled "Performance-Based Pedagogy: Enhancement of 21st Century Speaking Skills of Senior High School" seeks to contribute valuable insights to the existing literature by examining the nuances of incorporating performance-based approaches in the unique context of Philippine Senior High School education. By addressing this gap, the study aims to highlight the potential benefits of Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing critical communication skills that are essential for the modern workforce. Additionally, it will provide educators with practical strategies and evidence-based practices tailored to the educational needs of Filipino students, thereby fostering a more effective and engaging learning environment.

In conclusion, the study "Performance-Based Pedagogy: Enhancement of 21st Century Speaking Skills of Senior High School" embarks on a comprehensive exploration of the potential impact of Performance-Based Pedagogy on Grade 11 learners at Cayambanan National High School in Urdaneta, Pangasinan for the academic year 2023-2024. By focusing on the assessment of current speaking skill levels, investigating the effectiveness of Performance-Based Pedagogy in addressing linguistic challenges and fostering a supportive learning environment, and examining the potential integration of this pedagogical approach into the language curriculum, the research seeks to provide valuable insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers.

Research Questions

This research aimed to investigate the effect of Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing the 21st century speaking skills of Senior High School in Cayambanan National High School of academic year 2023-2024? Specifically, it aimed to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of the controlled group and experimental group across the two types of speeches:
 - 1.1. prepared speech, and
 - 1.2. extemporaneous speech?
2. Is there a significant difference between the performance of the controlled group and the experimental group?
3. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the 21st century public speaking skills of Grade 11 learners?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a true-experimental research design to further explore the effect of Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing the 21st century speaking skills of Senior High School. The experimental research design was used since it aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables. This method encompasses the manipulation of an independent variable and the random allocation of participants across varied groups, experimental group, and controlled group, to analyze the impact on a dependent variable (Zubai, 2023).

In this study, two groups of subjects were randomly assigned as experimental group and controlled group. A set of activities was given to both groups where the Experimental Group accomplished the task anchored by Performance-Based Pedagogy. The Controlled Group, on the other hand, used the current learning materials in Oral Communication. Afterward, the scores of the learners in the given activities were compared to determine if there was a significant difference in the performance of the two groups.

Participants

The study focused on the population of Senior High School Grade 11 – General Academic Strand learners at Cayambanan National High School who were presently enrolled for the academic year 2023-2024. The target population encompassed two class sections, each comprising 33 and 35 learners, respectively. The distribution of learners within these sections was heterogeneous, reflecting diversity in various characteristics.

Employing a random sampling technique, 15 learners were randomly chosen from both Section A and Section B, resulting in a total of 30 subjects for the study. A total number of 15 subjects were categorized for the controlled group, and the other 15 subjects were members of the experimental.

The use of random sampling ensured a representative and unbiased selection of participants, contributing to the validity and generalizability of the study's findings. Random sampling is a method of selecting a sample from a larger population in such a way that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample. In other words, each member of the population has an equal and independent opportunity of being chosen.

Instrument

The research study employed an analytical scoring rubric as its principal data gathering instrument to evaluate the 21st century public speaking skills of participating learners from both the controlled and experimental. For each type of speech, an analytical rubric was used with a scale of 5 (Excellent), 4 (Good), 3 (Fair), 2 (Poor), and 1 (Needs Improvement) to comprehensively assess various criteria related to speech delivery. It is important to note that the criteria of the rubric were made to follow Oral Communication's curriculum guide as it stated the six components of 21st Century speaking skills according to Leonita et al. (2023): Clarity, Coherence, and Conciseness, Fluency, Adaptability and Versatility, and Proficiency in Nonverbal Communication such as body language, gestures, and facial expressions, and Rapport with Audience.

The rubric used in the study was adapted from the Valencia College Rubrics for the Assessment of Oral Communication: Delivery, which itself was based on CLAST & SAT Writing Rubrics (2019). It is important to note that both rubrics were modified to effectively assess the subjects' performances according to the six components of 21st century speaking skills.

Hence, the rubric was examined and validated by three secondary English language teachers to ensure the appropriateness of the tool in measuring the speech performances of learners. The content validation resulted in scores of 5 from Validator A, 4.78 from Validator B, and 5 from Validator C. These results reflect a strong consensus on the tool's effectiveness, reliability, and accuracy, with an overall average score of 4.93 which means that the rubric is Highly Valid. This high level of validity confirms that the rubric is exceptionally well-suited for evaluating speech performances, providing a reliable and effective measure for the intended educational assessments.

Procedure

The study used a true experimental research design to investigate the effect of Performance-Based Pedagogy on the enhancement of 21st Century Speaking Skills of Senior High School Learners. The research consisted of two groups: a controlled group and an experimental group, each comprising 15 subjects.

The data gathering procedure for this study commenced with the acquisition of permissions and consents necessary for ethical research conduct. Initially, formal letters were drafted seeking approval from Dr. Paulo Cenas, the Executive Director of the PSU School of Advanced Studies, and Sir Aguedo Fernandez, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent of Urdaneta City. These communications outlined the study's objectives, methodology, and potential implications.

Subsequently, a request was made to Sir Gino T. Aspiras, Principal IV of Cayambanan National High School (CNHS), to allow data collection from Grade 11 students enrolled at CNHS. This step was pivotal in obtaining access to the target population and securing cooperation from the school administration.

Finally, informed consent was sought from the Grade 11 students through a detailed letter explaining the purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations of the study. Throughout the process, strict adherence to ethical guidelines was maintained, prioritizing participant welfare, voluntary participation, and confidentiality of data. All interactions with school authorities and students were conducted with professionalism, respect, and transparency, ensuring the integrity and validity of the research endeavor.

After seeking consent from the necessary authorities, the data gathering for the experiment began. As the first step, both the Controlled and Experimental groups received a lecture centering on the instruction of the different modes of speech delivery: prepared and extemporaneous speech. The controlled group only received traditional instruction and activities on delivering prepared and extemporaneous speeches based on the curriculum and conventional learning materials in Oral Communication. Meanwhile, the Experimental Group underwent speaking activities as a performance-based intervention to supplement the instructions on delivering the two kinds of speeches.

Performance-based pedagogy, as outlined by Hollandsworth et al. (2020), is an instructional methodology that underscores students' capacity to perform specific skills as a direct outcome of instruction. Within this paradigm, students are expected not only to possess knowledge but also to demonstrate its practical application, emphasizing active engagement and skill demonstration.

For the enhancement of the subjects' skills in delivering a prepared speech, the performance task given to them was spoken word poetry. Spoken word poetry is an oral performance art that is based mainly on the piece as well as the performer's aesthetic qualities. The researcher used spoken word poetry as a dynamic model for teaching learners how to deliver a compelling prepared speech by showcasing the power of voice modulation, rhythm, and expressive delivery. This approach not only refines speech delivery skills but also encourages learners to find their voice and express complex ideas in an engaging and impactful manner.

For extemporaneous speech, the performance task used is prompt-driven storytelling. Prompt-driven storytelling is an exercise where individuals are given prompts or cues, such as words, images, or situations, to inspire them to create and narrate stories spontaneously. Participants respond to these prompts by constructing ideas on the spot, often without prior preparation or planning. The goal is to encourage creativity, quick thinking, and the ability to construct coherent and engaging stories in real-time.

This exercise is commonly used in educational settings, public speaking training, and creative writing workshops to develop storytelling skills, spontaneity, and the ability to think on one's feet. Prompt-driven story development allows learners to seamlessly integrate the essential elements of extemporaneous speech—such as introduction, main points, transitions, and conclusion. It encourages adaptability and flexibility, key qualities in extemporaneous speaking. Learners learn to think on their feet while maintaining structured and engaging ideas.

Following the intervention, both the controlled and experimental groups were subjected to a post-test to evaluate the impact of the Performance-Based Pedagogy on their speaking skills. The final phase of data collection encompassed the post-test, wherein subjects were assigned the final task of delivering a prepared and extemporaneous speech. The objective of the posttest was to evaluate the impact of each performance task administered before the prepared speech and extemporaneous speech presentations, aiming to determine their effect on enhancing the subjects' performance. The learners' performances were graded by three English teachers in the school using a rubric.

Data Analysis

This research employed diverse statistical methods to address the outlined research questions. For the first research question, descriptive statistics were applied to assess the performance of both the controlled and experimental group. This analysis relied on the scores obtained by the learners through utilizing a rubric to measure their proficiency.

To address the second research question, the independent sample t-test was used to determine whether a statistically significant difference exists between the performance of the controlled and experimental group in their 21st century public speaking skill tasks. This statistical analysis helped assess the effect of Performance-Based Pedagogy as an intervention in enhancing the learners' 21st century speaking skills. The independent samples t-test compares the means of two independent groups to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different. The independent samples t-test compares are a parametric test.

Lastly, the third research question is dedicated to outlining a proposed action plan aimed at implementing Performance-Based Pedagogy to enhance the speaking skills of Senior High School students. This plan seeks to provide a detailed process that integrates innovative teaching methods tailored to improve oral communication abilities. By focusing on Performance-Based Pedagogy, the SOP aims to establish a structured approach that incorporates practical activities, assessments, and feedback mechanisms to foster a supportive learning environment.

Results and Discussion

This section delineates the empirical results derived from data analysis, delves into their implications, and elucidates their significance in addressing the research questions or objectives.

Performance of the Subjects Across the Two Types Of Speeches

On the Descriptive Statistics along with Prepared Speech

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics or the numerical or graphical summaries of data that provide insights into its central tendency, variability, and distribution. This section provides a comparison between the performance of the Controlled Group and the Experimental Group in terms of their prepared speech performance.

Table 1. *Descriptive Statistics on the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Prepared Speech*

Statistic	Controlled Group	Experimental Group
Mean	22.56	25.09
Standard Deviation	3.79	3.35
Minimum	16.67	17.67
Maximum	30.00	30.00
Skewness	0.63	-0.93
Kurtosis	0.34	1.40

Considering the means, the Experimental Group outperformed the Controlled Group, with a mean score of 25.09 compared to 22.56. Additionally, the variability in scores was lower in the Experimental Group, as indicated by a smaller standard deviation of 3.35 compared to 3.79 in the Controlled Group. While both groups achieved the same maximum score of 30.00, the Experimental Group had a slightly higher minimum score of 17.67 compared to 16.67 in the Controlled Group.

This suggests that the intervention applied in the Experimental Group was more effective in raising overall performance levels and in producing more consistent results among participants. The study of Herbein et al. (2017) had similar findings which indicated that students who underwent speech performance practices resulted to have more enhanced speaking skills. These underscore the importance of incorporating performance-based approaches in teaching 21st century speaking skills to foster better learning outcomes among students.

Moreover, Figure 1 presents the histogram illustrating the shape of the data distribution for the performance of the Controlled Group and prepared group in terms of prepared speech.

Figure 1. *Histogram of the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Prepared Speech*

As shown in Figure 1, the Controlled Group's scores exhibited a slight positive skew, indicating that more scores were clustered toward the lower end, while the Experimental Group's scores showed a negative skew, suggesting a concentration toward the higher end. Furthermore, the kurtosis values highlight differences in the shape of the distributions, with the Experimental Group's scores being more peaked around the mean, indicating a more concentrated distribution compared to the Controlled Group. Overall, these statistics demonstrate that the Experimental Group displayed both a higher average performance and a more consistent distribution of scores compared to the Controlled Group in the context of prepared speech.

In summary, these findings underscore the effectiveness of the Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing students' prepared speech performance. The higher mean score, lower variability, and more concentrated distribution of scores observed in the Experimental Group collectively highlight the benefits of employing this pedagogical method for improving speaking skills among students.

On the Level of Performance of Subjects along with Prepared Speech

Table 2 provides a visual representation of the performance levels achieved by both the Controlled Group and the Experimental Group in terms of the prepared speech performances of the subjects. This table offers a comparative analysis to discern differences between the two groups and evaluate the effectiveness of Performance-Based Pedagogy.

Table 2. *Level of Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Prepared Speech*

Level of Performance	Score range	Prepared Speech			
		Controlled Group (n=15)		Experimental Group (n=15)	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Excellent	26-30	4	26.7	11	73.3
Good	21-25	9	60.0	4	26.7
Fair	15-20	2	13.3	0	0.0
Poor	10-14	0	0.0	0	0.0
Needs Improvement	9 & below	0	0.0	0	0.0

In the prepared speech category, 60 percent of learners from the Controlled Group were categorized as Good, with only 13.3 percent categorized as Fair. Meanwhile, the Experimental Group had 73.3 percent of learners achieving Excellent scores, with 26.7 percent falling into the Good range.

This result suggests that exposure of Grade 11 learners to Performance-Based Pedagogy speaking activities has equipped learners with the necessary skills to effectively structure and convey their ideas in a prepared speech format. As highlighted by Hibbard (2020) in "Teacher's Guide to Performance-Based Learning and Assessment," such preparatory tasks play a crucial role in enhancing fluency and adaptability among students. Through engaging in a spectrum of performance tasks, students not only gain confidence in expressing themselves but also develop the agility to adjust their communication style to suit varied contexts, thereby refining their adaptability skills.

Additionally, these tasks allow students to receive immediate feedback, enabling them to identify areas for improvement and refine their speaking skills accordingly. Overall, the combination of performance tasks and speeches creates a comprehensive learning experience that fosters fluency and adaptability in students' communication abilities.

Moreover, in an article written by Tait (2017) titled "Delivering your speech: the power of nonverbal communication", it was stated that speaking effectively encompasses more than just projecting a professional tone and exuding confidence in one's voice; it extends to the proficient use of nonverbal cues to convey the true impact of the message. Nonverbal communication, which includes gestures, facial expressions, and body language, plays a significant role in conveying meaning beyond verbal language. Integrating performance tasks before delivering a prepared speech can also contribute to improving students' nonverbal cues.

On the Descriptive Statistics along Extemporaneous Speech

As for the other type of speech observed in this research, Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group which revealed differences in their extemporaneous speech performance.

Table 3. *Descriptive Statistics on the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Extemporaneous Speech*

Statistic	Controlled Group	Experimental Group
Mean	23.31	26.13
Standard Deviation	3.36	2.79
Minimum	18.33	21.33
Maximum	30.00	30.00
Skewness	0.60	-0.73
Kurtosis	-0.27	-0.39

The Experimental Group has a mean score of 26.13, surpassing the Controlled Group's mean score of 23.31. Moreover, the variability in performance within the experimental group was lower, as evidenced by its smaller standard deviation of 2.79 compared to the controlled group's 3.36. While both groups achieved the same maximum score of 30.00, the experimental group demonstrated a higher minimum score of 21.33, contrasting with the controlled group's minimum score of 18.33.

In addition, Figure 2 presents a histogram detailing the skewness and kurtosis of performance scores for both the controlled and experimental groups in extemporaneous speech. This graphical representation provides essential insights into the distributional characteristics of the data, highlighting any asymmetry, tails, or peaks in the score distributions.

Figure 2 shows the skewness values which further illustrated differences in the distribution of scores between the groups, with the Controlled Group's scores being positively skewed (0.60) and the Experimental Group's scores showing a negative skew (-0.73).

Additionally, both groups exhibited similar kurtosis values, indicating that the distributions were relatively close to a normal distribution. Overall, these statistics indicate that the experimental group outperformed the controlled group in extemporaneous speech, achieving higher average scores with less variability in performance.

Figure 2. Histogram of the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Extemporaneous Speech

Overall, these results suggest that the performance-based pedagogy employed in the Experimental Group led to higher average scores and a more consistent level of performance in extemporaneous speech tasks compared to the traditional instructional approach used in the Controlled Group. This underscores the effectiveness of performance-based pedagogy in enhancing students' extemporaneous speaking skills.

On the Level of Performance of Subjects along with Extemporaneous Speech

In terms of the level of performance, Table 4 depicts the performance levels of both the Experimental Group and the Controlled Group concerning the extemporaneous speech performances of the subjects.

Table 4. Level of Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Extemporaneous Speech

Level of Performance	Score range	Extemporaneous Speech			
		Controlled Group (n=15)		Experimental Group (n=15)	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Excellent	26-30	2	13.3	10	66.7
Good	21-25	10	66.7	3	20.0
Fair	15-20	3	20.0	2	13.3
Poor	10-14	0	0.0	0	0.0
Needs Improvement	9 & below	0	0.0	0	0.0

As indicated in Table 4, 66.7 percent or 10 out of 15 learners in the Controlled Group were rated as Good, with only 13.3 percent or 2 out of 15 learners achieving an Excellent score in their extemporaneous speech performance. In contrast, the Experimental Group had 66.7 percent or 10 out of 15 learners achieving an Excellent score, while 13.3 percent or 2 out of 15 learners were rated as Fair.

This result underscores the adaptability and fluency of Experimental Group learners in extemporaneous speaking situations, potentially attributed to their engagement with performance-based activities, which likely fostered spontaneity and confidence in expressing ideas on the spot.

There are a lot of reasons why learners, most especially ESL learners, have difficulties in public speaking, such as lack of ideas to tell, lack of vocabulary to express the ideas, lack of the chance to speak, and lack of interesting teaching method that can motivate them to speak (Zuhriyah, 2017). With the use of Performance-Based Pedagogy which is an instructional approach that utilizes performance-based tasks focused on giving students opportunities to apply their actual speaking skills in the teaching and learning process, learners are helped in improving their public speaking skills by engaging learners through different speaking activities (Peters, 2021).

In an article written by Ameresekere (2023) called "Power of Story Telling and Public Speaking", he stated that prompt-driven storytelling exercises can significantly enhance students' extemporaneous speech skills by fostering creativity, spontaneity, and adaptability. These exercises require students to think quickly on their feet and respond to prompts or cues with impromptu stories. As students engage in these activities, they become more adept at organizing their thoughts coherently and articulating ideas fluently under

pressure. Additionally, prompt-driven storytelling encourages students to think creatively and imaginatively, as they must construct ideas on the spot. This process helps them develop their storytelling abilities, enabling them to effectively engage and captivate their audience during extemporaneous speeches. Furthermore, regular practice with prompt-driven storytelling builds students' confidence in their ability to speak spontaneously and handle unexpected situations, ultimately strengthening their extemporaneous speech skills.

Moreover, in an article titled "How to Develop Extemporaneous and Public Speaking Skills" by Berlinsky-Schine (2017), it was stated that extemporaneous speaking skills can be enhanced through on-the-spot speaking activities by providing opportunities for individuals to practice thinking quickly, organizing their thoughts effectively, and delivering coherent speeches without prior preparation. These activities typically involve impromptu speaking tasks where participants are given a topic or prompt and a short amount of time to prepare their remarks before speaking. By engaging in such activities regularly, individuals develop the ability to articulate their ideas clearly, respond spontaneously to various topics, and adapt their communication style to different contexts.

Additionally, on-the-spot speaking activities, such as prompt-driven storytelling, help individuals become more comfortable with public speaking, boost their confidence, and refine their delivery skills as they learn to convey their message convincingly under pressure.

On the Graphical Representation of Scores of the Subjects across the Two Types of Speeches

To further show the differences among the performance of groups, this scatterplot depicted in Figure 3 presents a visual representation of the performance scores achieved by learners from both the controlled group and the experimental group across two distinct types of speeches: prepared and extemporaneous.

Figure 3. Scatterplot of the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group across the Two Types of Speeches

Figure 3 indicates that the scores of the experimental group are generally higher, with most data points falling within the range of 24 to 30. Conversely, the scores of the Controlled Group tend to be lower, with data points clustering more towards the lower end of the score range. This pattern suggests that, on average, learners in the Experimental Group perform better in both types of speeches compared to those in the controlled group. The scatter plot effectively illustrates this difference in performance between the two groups across the two types of speeches.

Overall, the results in the level of performance across the two types of speeches indicate that learners exposed to performance-based speaking activities displayed a higher tendency for achieving excellence in both prepared and extemporaneous speeches compared to their counterparts in the Controlled Group. These findings highlight the effect of Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing learners' public speaking skills and underscore the importance of innovative instructional approaches in fostering communicative competence.

Similar effects of the impact of Performance-Based Pedagogy on the enhancement of 21st century public speaking skills of learners were also found in the study of Menggo & Gunnas (2022) titled "College Student's Perception of Performance-Based Learning Use in Boosting Speaking Ability," which focused on examining the implementation of performance-based pedagogy and revealing students' reactions to this intervention in speaking classes.

This research, conducted over a period of three months from November 2020 to January 2021, employed a quantitative descriptive approach. The research enlisted 49 participants drawn from two inaugural English Education Study Program classes at Universitas Katolik Indonesia Santu Paulus Ruteng. Findings revealed a beneficial effect of performance-based tasks on speaking ability, with a post-test average reaching 76. As a result, educators are urged to incorporate this assessment approach into their speaking pedagogy. Through the implementation of performance-based tasks over three months, students demonstrated notable enhancements in speaking abilities. Similar to this study, these results underscore the significance of incorporating Performance-Based approaches in speaking classes, advocating for a transition towards interactive and experiential learning methods to cultivate students' communication

proficiency.

Difference Between the Performance of the Subjects Across the Two Types of Speeches

On the Difference between the Performance of Subjects along with Prepared Speech

For the second research question, Table 5 displays the results of the independent samples t-test, which was conducted to assess the difference in performance between the controlled group and experimental group in prepared speeches by comparing the mean scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

Table 5. *Difference between the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Prepared Speech*

Type of Speech	Controlled Group		Experimental Group		Mean Difference	tc	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Prepared Speech	23.31	3.36	26.13	2.79	2.82	2.51*	0.018

*Significant at 5% level

^{ns}Not significant

As shown in the table, the mean score for the Controlled Group for prepared speech stood at 23.31, with a standard deviation of 3.36, while the Experimental Group achieved a higher mean score of 26.13, with a slightly lower standard deviation of 2.79, indicating that participants in the Experimental Group performed better in delivering prepared speeches. The calculated t-value of 2.51 signaled a considerable difference in performance, with a p-value of 0.018, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, confirming statistical significance. Consequently, the results suggest that subjects in the Experimental Group outperformed their counterparts in the Controlled Group in delivering prepared speeches, illustrating the effectiveness of the experimental intervention in enhancing speech delivery skills.

According to the National Speech & Debate Association (2017), a prepared speech is one of the most common types of speech where a speaker was given the topic in advance, had time to do background research on it, and has practiced delivering the speech. A prepared speech could be a manuscript or memorized speech.

In delivering a prepared speech, it is crucial to focus on thorough preparation, audience awareness, confidence, clarity, engagement, structure, authenticity, adaptability, and rehearsal. In this research, the Experimental Group was given spoken word poetry as the performance-based activity to enhance the learners' skills in delivering the prepared speech.

According to Metusalem et al. (2021) in an article written for Partnership for 21st century learning, performance-based speaking activities enhance students' prepared speech skills by providing them with opportunities to engage in meaningful and practical speaking tasks. These activities often involve simulating real-life speaking situations, such as debates, presentations, role-plays, or discussions.

One keyway performance-based activities improve prepared speech skills is by promoting active learning. Instead of passively listening to lectures or reading about public speaking techniques, students actively participate in speaking tasks, which helps them apply speaking principles. Furthermore, performance-based speaking activities foster confidence by providing learners with opportunities to practice speaking in a supportive and non-threatening environment. As students become more comfortable expressing themselves and receiving feedback, their fear of public speaking diminishes, and they become more willing to take risks and experiment with different speaking techniques (Metusalem et al., 2021).

On the Difference between the Performance of Subjects along Extemporaneous Speech

As for the other type of speech, Table 6 presents the difference between the Controlled Group and Experimental group in extemporaneous speeches in determining if the Performance-Based Pedagogy intervention had enhanced the extemporaneous speech performance of the Experimental Group.

Table 6. *Difference between the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group along Extemporaneous Speech*

Type of Speech	Controlled Group		Experimental Group		Mean Difference	tc	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Extemporaneous Speech	22.56	3.79	25.09	3.35	2.53	1.94 ^{ns}	0.063

*Significant at 5% level

^{ns}Not significant

The table shows that the Controlled Group's mean score of 22.56 and SD of 3.79, compared to the Experimental Group demonstrated a higher mean score of 25.09, with a standard deviation of 3.35. Considering these figures, the calculated mean difference of 2.53 did not achieve statistical significance. With a t-value of 1.94, the observed difference was not deemed statistically significant at the 5 percent level ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that, although there was a numerical advantage in favor of the Experimental Group, it was not statistically meaningful, indicating that factors beyond the instructional technique may have influenced performance in extemporaneous speaking scenarios.

In the context of extemporaneous speech, the study's results reveal a noteworthy trend that although the difference in performance

between the Experimental Group and Controlled Group did not attain statistical significance, the Experimental Group obtained a higher average score of 25.09 compared to the Controlled Group's average of 22.56. While this difference did not meet the threshold for statistical significance, it is essential to recognize the potential implications of these mean scores. The higher average score achieved by the Experimental Group suggests that the students who engaged in prompt-driven storytelling activities as part of the performance-based activity have demonstrated enhanced performance compared to their counterparts in the Controlled Group.

Prompt-driven storytelling played a pivotal role in shaping the performance of the Experimental Group. By engaging in activities that prompt students to construct ideas spontaneously around specific themes or prompts, such as personal experiences or societal issues, students develop essential skills for extemporaneous speaking. These skills include the ability to generate ideas quickly, organize thoughts coherently, and communicate effectively under time constraints.

The practice of prompt-driven storytelling encourages students to think creatively and adaptively, preparing them to respond adeptly to impromptu speaking situations. Stephen (2020) in his article "The Art of Speaking" stated that speakers may find it challenging to deliver a speech using extemporaneous speech style to make the delivery organized, conversational, and responsive to the audience and context. An extemporaneous delivery will require that the speaker use a limited number of notes, and avoid a read or memorized presentation; instead, the speaker should practice and rehearse as many times as needed to become familiar with the subject and deliver the content using their own words and a conversational style. Naturally, these could be a really challenging task specifically for speakers using a second language.

Despite the challenges of delivering an extemporaneous speech, interventions such as the use prompt-driven storytelling activity may allow learners to prepare and perform a well-delivered speech. Performance-based pedagogical activities, such as prompt-driven storytelling or spontaneous storytelling, can be highly beneficial in preparing learners for extemporaneous speech delivery in several ways. Prompt-driven or spontaneous storytelling is an art form that thrives on the magic of the moment just like an extemporaneous speech. It is about harnessing the power of imagination, intuition, and quick thinking to create engaging ideas on the spot. It requires the ability to observe and connect with the audience, adapting the story to suit the context and captivate their attention (Murugan, 2023).

He further added in his article entitled "The Art of Spontaneous Storytelling" that these activities encourage learners to think quickly and creatively on their feet, simulating the spontaneous nature of extemporaneous speaking. By responding to prompts or improvising stories based on given topics, learners develop the ability to generate ideas rapidly and organize them into coherent thoughts, essential skills for delivering extemporaneous speeches.

On the Difference between the Performance of the Subjects across the Two Types of Speeches

Further, Figure 4 presents a profile plot which is a graphical representation that displays the pattern of data points across different levels of one or more variables. This graphical representation illustrates the difference in performance between the Controlled Group and the Experimental Group across two types of speeches.

Figure 4. Profile Plot of the Difference between the Performance of the Controlled Group and Experimental Group Across the Two Types of Speeches

The plot indicates that the Experimental Group consistently outperforms the Controlled Group across both types of speeches, as evidenced by the higher margin of scores associated with the experimental group. Specifically, the scores of the Experimental Group range from 26 to 25, indicating a consistently higher performance level compared to the Controlled Group, whose scores range from 24 to 23.

Additionally, the observed grand mean, representing the average performance across both groups and both types of speeches, is described as slightly above 24. This suggests that, on average, subjects in both groups perform slightly above the midpoint of the score range.

Overall, these findings underscore the effectiveness of the Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing the subjects' 21st century speaking skills specifically in terms of their performance in prepared speeches, as evidenced by the significant difference between the Experimental and Controlled Groups. However, the absence of statistical significance in extemporaneous speeches suggests that further exploration into additional variables impacting extemporaneous speaking performance may be necessary. Such exploration could help refine instructional approaches and better tailor them to meet the diverse needs of learners in various speaking contexts. Moreover, these results highlight the importance of continued research and refinement in educational practices to optimize learning outcomes and promote students' speaking proficiency across different speech types.

Comparable to this study, Safitri et al. (2020) aimed to improve students' speaking skills through task-based learning in their research titled "Improving Students' Speaking Skills through Task-Based Learning: An Action Research at the English Department." Initial assessments revealed students' struggles due to limited language knowledge, leading to a lack of confidence in verbal expression. Task-based learning was then implemented in a semester-long course involving fifteen third-semester students, resulting in pre-test and post-test evaluations, alongside interviews and observations for data collection and analysis. The study of Safitri et al.'s reveals that students often struggle due to insufficient speaking practices, echoing the issues addressed in this study. Moreover, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of performance-based learning in enhancing various aspects of speaking skills, such as accuracy, vocabulary usage, and clarity.

Proposed Action Plan on Enhancing the 21st Century Speaking Skills of Senior High School Through Performance-Based Pedagogy

The Action Plan on Enhancing the 21st Century Speaking Skills of Senior High School through Performance-Based Pedagogy serves as the answer to the third research question, focusing on enhancing students' 21st century speaking skills by using the Performance-Based Pedagogy as intervention. It outlines a series of structured activities designed to immerse senior high school students in performance-based learning experiences.

An action plan is the suited output for this research due to its practicality and implementation potential. Similar to the study of Safitri et al. (2020) titled "Improving Students' Speaking Skills through Task-Based Learning: An Action Research at the English Department", which also focused on enhancing learners' speaking abilities through actual speaking performances or tasks, an action plan was the chosen research output.

By outlining specific steps and strategies based on the findings of this study, the action plan below proposed a structured approach to applying Performance-Based Pedagogy to enhance 21st century skills among Senior High School students.

Matrix 1. Action Plan On Enhancing The 21st Century Speaking Skills Of Senior High School Through

<i>ACTION STEPS</i>	<i>RESPONSIBLE PARTIES</i>	<i>TIMELINE</i>	<i>RESOURCES NEEDED</i>
1. Introduction to Performance-based Pedagogy	Teachers, Learners	Week 1 (4 days)	Lesson plans, learning materials
2. Performance-based Workshops	Teachers, Learners	Week 2 (4 days)	Workshops, seminars, learning materials
3. Feedback Sessions	Teachers, Learners	Week 3 (2 days)	Classroom space, learning materials
4. Reflection and Practice	Teachers, Learners	Week 3 (2 days)	Classroom space, learning materials
5. Speech Performance and Assessment	Teachers, Learners	Week 4 (4 days)	Assessment tools, rubrics

The matrix shows the activities incorporated into the study which encompasses an approach aimed at effectively implementing Performance-Based Pedagogy to enhance students' speaking skills. Firstly, students are introduced to the principles and methodologies of Performance-Based Pedagogy, providing them with a foundational understanding of the approach. Following this introduction, performance-based workshops are conducted, which integrate elements of spoken word poetry and prompt-driven storytelling. These workshops serve as interactive platforms for students to engage in hands-on learning experiences, allowing them to explore and practice various speaking techniques in a supportive environment. Additionally, feedback sessions are integrated into the process, providing students with constructive feedback on their performance and opportunities for reflection and improvement. Finally, speech performance assessments are conducted to evaluate students' progress and proficiency in both prepared speech delivery, utilizing spoken word poetry techniques, and extemporaneous speech delivery, employing prompt-driven storytelling strategies.

Below is a more comprehensive description of the activities integrated in the action plan:

Introduction to Performance-Based Pedagogy (Week 1):

- Learners will be introduced to the concept of Performance-Based Pedagogy, emphasizing its significance in improving their 21st century public speaking skills.
- Through interactive discussions, learners will explore the role of storytelling as a powerful tool in conveying ideas and emotions.

Performance-Based Workshop (Week 2):

- This immersion will consist of workshops focusing on learning and practicing performance-based activities, such as spoken word poetry and prompt-driven storytelling.
- Learners will be taught the relationship between the performance-based activities in improving their skills in delivering speeches like prepared and extemporaneous speeches.
- Learners will have the opportunity to perform various types of speeches, integrating the speaking skills learned from performance-based activities into their presentations.

Feedback Sessions (Week 3):

- Feedback sessions will provide students with valuable insights into their storytelling techniques and public speaking performance.
- Both teacher-learner and peer feedback sessions will be conducted to offer comprehensive feedback and foster a supportive learning environment.

Reflection and Practice (Week 3):

- During these two days, learners will engage in reflective activities aimed at assessing their progress in public speaking.
- Learners will have the opportunity to reflect on their strengths and areas for improvement, considering feedback received from previous activities.
- Additionally, learners will conduct additional practice sessions to further refine their public speaking skills.
- Through guided reflection and targeted practice, learners will consolidate their learning and continue to enhance their proficiency in 21st century public speaking.

Speech Performance and Assessment (Week 4):

- Students will deliver speeches which are focused on the components of characteristics of 21st century speaking skills: Clarity, Cohesion and Conciseness, Fluency, Adaptability, Versatility, and Proficiency and Nonverbal Communication.
- Their performances will be assessed to evaluate the effect of Performance-Based pedagogy in the 21st century in public speaking or students.
- This comprehensive action plan is designed to immerse students in performance-based learning experiences, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in 21st century public speaking.

Conclusions

From the findings, the following conclusions are drawn: In prepared speeches, the Experimental Group display a better performance, achieving an Excellent level compared to the Controlled Group's Good performance. Similarly, in extemporaneous speeches, the Experimental Group once again excelled, demonstrating an Excellent level of performance compared to the Controlled Group's Good performance. These underscores the effectiveness of the Performance-Based Pedagogy intervention, as evidenced by the superior performance of the Experimental Group, thereby emphasizing the importance of innovative pedagogical approaches in enhancing learners' public speaking skills.

The research findings suggest that the Performance-Based activity utilized by the Experimental Group led to a significant difference in performance in prepared speeches compared to the Controlled Group. However, no significant difference was observed between the groups in extemporaneous speeches. Despite this, the Experimental Group still achieved a higher average score in extemporaneous speeches, indicating a potential benefit of the Performance-Based Pedagogy in enhancing overall communication skills.

The action plan outlined in Matrix 1 is focused on proposing actionable steps to enhance the 21st century public speaking skills of Grade 11 learners. By integrating Performance-Based Pedagogy into teaching the two modes of speech delivery, the plan offers a structured approach to cultivating effective communication abilities. The plan's emphasis on experiential learning and feedback mechanisms underscores its commitment to fostering a supportive environment where students can thrive as articulate and confident communicators in the modern world.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are presented: First, it is recommended to incorporate Performance-Based Pedagogy activities, such as spoken word poetry, into the Grade 11 Oral Communication curriculum, particularly for prepared speech instruction. Integrating spoken word poetry into the instructional approach offers several benefits that can significantly enhance students' speaking abilities. Second, it is advised to explore alternative Performance-Based activities for enhancing extemporaneous speech skills. Extemporaneous speaking demands quick thinking, effective organization of thoughts, and

confident delivery under pressure, making it a particularly daunting task for learners. While prompt-driven storytelling has shown promise in bolstering these abilities, it is important to recognize that a single approach may not meet the diverse needs and learning styles of all students. Lastly, the proposed action plan for enhancing the 21st-century speaking skills of Senior High School students through Performance-Based Pedagogy is recommended for implementation. This plan has demonstrated effectiveness and is expected to lead to improvements in both prepared and extemporaneous speech performances among learners.

References

- Ameresekere, T. (2023). Power of Story Telling in Public Speaking. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/power-story-telling-public-speaking-tharindu-ameresekere/>.
- Anggini, S. & Arjulayana, A. (2021). Analysis Student's Speaking Performance as an Academic Speaker's Practice. *Globish: An English-Indonesian Journal for English, Education, and Culture*. 10. 58. 10.31000/globish.v10i1.3943.
- Akbar, F. (2014). The role of reading in improving speaking skill in the context of teaching English as a foreign language. *International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*, 2(4), 92-98.
- Apriyanti, N.F., Leonito, N., Krismayani, W. (2023). Speaking Skill in 21st-Century: Learners' Perceptions And Challenges In English Language Teaching.
- Berlinsky-Schine. L. (2017). How to Develop Extemporaneous and Public Speaking Skills. <https://blog.collegevine.com/how-to-develop-extemporaneous-and-public-speaking-skills>.
- Bohra, B. & Khan, M.R. (2023). "Language Proficiency: A Complex Construct". https://ijariie.com/AdminUploadPdf/Language_Proficiency__A_Complex_Construct_ijariie21061.pdf.
- British Council Global. (2016). Speaking skills workshop through storytelling. <https://www.britishcouncil.in/events/speaking-skills-workshop-through-storytelling#:~:text=When%20a%20child%20listens%20to,and%20care%20for%20their%20audience>.
- Brown, H. D. (2004). *Language Assessment: Principles and Classroom Practices*. New York: Addison Wesley Longman Inc.
- Caoili, R. (2007). *Education for All by 2015: Will we make it? The Philippines country case study: Education for All Global Monitoring Report 2008*. Paris, France: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Castillejo, S.P. (2018). Breaking Down the Affective Filter and Building Confidence with Extempore. <https://extemporeapp.com/blog/breaking-down-the-affective-filter-and-building-confidence-with-extempore>.
- Czerkawski, B. & Berti, M. (2020). Language learning in the 21st century: current status and future directions. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346814645_Language_learning_in_the_21st_century_current_status_and_future_directions
- Dimova, S. (2022). Performance-based Speaking Tests: Possibilities in Local Language Testing. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1361396.pdf>.
- Ellis, R (2003). *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Fisher, D. & Frey, N. (2007). *Checking for Understanding: Formative Assessment Techniques for Your Classroom*. California: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development (ASCD).
- Fulcher, G. (2018). Assessing spoken production. In J. I. Lontos & M. DelliCarpini (Eds.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching* (pp. 1-6). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235>.
- Gaudry-Routledge. M. E. & Binder, M. J. (2018). Educators' Perceptions of Performance-Based Approaches in Teaching the Youth. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1261332.pdf>.
- Harmer, J. (2002). *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. London: Pearson Education.
- Hibbard, K.M. (2020). *Teacher's Guide to Performance-Based Learning and Assessment*. <https://www.schoolcraft.edu/oca/performance-based-learning/>.
- Jati, G. (2017). Perspective on ICT in teaching and learning listening & speaking in the 21st century : beyond classroom wall. *Journal of Teaching & Learning English in Multicultural Contexts*, 1(1), 16–29.
- Johnson, P. (2009). The 21st century skills movement. *Educational Leadership*, 67, 11.
- Kayi, H. (2016). *Teaching Speaking: Activities to Promote Speaking in a Second Language*. <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Kayi-TeachingSpeaking.html>.
- Kelly, M. (2019). Authentic Ways to Develop Performance-Based Activities. <https://www.thoughtco.com/ideas-for-performance-based-activities-7686>.

- Leonita, N. & Apriyanti, N. & Krismayani, N. & Joni, D. & Budiarta, I. K. (2023). Speaking Skill in 21st-Century: Students' Perceptions and Challenges In English Language Teaching. *Premise: Journal Of English Education*. 12. 614. 10.24127/Pj.V12i2.7262.
- Lucas, Stephen (2020). *The art of public speaking*. Paul Stob (Thirteenth ed.). New York, NY. ISBN 978-1-260-56948-3. OCLC 1195454930.
- Menggo, S. & Gunas, T. (2022). College Student's Perception of Performance-Based Assessment Use in Boosting Speaking Ability.
- Mercado, I. (2015). Problems encountered in the alternative learning system in Tanauan City. *International Journal of Education and Social Science*, 28(8), 16-28.
- Namaziandost, E., Hashemifardnia, A., & Shafiee, S. (2019). The impact of Opinion-gap, Reasoning-gap, and Information-gap tasks on EFL Learners' Speaking Fluency. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2019.1630150>.
- Nordquist, R. (2019). *Speech in Linguistics*. <https://www.thoughtco.com/speech-linguistics-1692121>.
- Philippine Exporters Confederation. (2023). Importance of Equipping Learners with 21st-century Competencies Cited. Philippine Exporters Confederation, Inc. <https://serp-p.pids.gov.ph/publication/public/view?slug=importance-of-equipping-learners-with-21st-century-competencies-cited>.
- Safitri, H., Rafli, Z., Dewanti, R., (2020). Improving Students' Speaking Skills through Task-Based Learning: An Action Research at the English Department. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v7i6.1647>.
- Silva, E. (2019). Measuring Skills for 21st-Century Learning. *Sage Journals*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/003172170909000905?journalCode=pdka>.
- Sparks, A. (2016) 9 Public Speaking Tips According to a Spoken Word Poet. <https://www.creativelive.com/blog/9-public-speaking-tips-according-spoken-word-poet/>.
- Taylor, P. (2017). Definition of Speech. https://www.academia.edu/35409413/Definition_of_a_speech.
- Tesol. (2022). How to Use Performance-Based Activities with Young Learners. <https://ontesol.com/blog/how-to-teach-english/teyl/how-to-use-performance-based-activities-and-projects-with-children/>.
- Tindowen, D. C et al. (2017). *Twenty-First-Century Skills of Alternative Learning System Learners*. Sage Publishing. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/2158244017726116>.
- Turk, C. (2003). *Effective Speaking: Communicating in Speech*. London: Spon Press.
- Varona, P. (2023). 21st Century Skills: Influence on Learners' Academic Performance.
- Wahed, A., & Hsu, Y. (2010). Cause and effect. In *Encyclopedia of Research Design* (Vol. 0, pp. 132-132). SAGE Publications, Inc., <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288>.
- Willis, M. (2017). *Methods of Speech Delivery*. <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/wm-publicspeaking/chapter/methods-of-speech-delivery/>.
- Zubai, A. M. (2023). Experimental Research Design-types & process. *Academia Open*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Girlie S. Gorgonia, MAEd

Schools Division of Urdaneta City
Department of Education – Philippines

Kristine May De Vera Casibang, PhD

Pangasinan State University – Philippines